

Work Motivation as a Mediator in the Influence of Work Environment and Burnout on Nurse Turnover at Husada Hospital

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ABSTRACT: Nurse turnover is one of the main challenges in various hospitals, including Husada Hospital. High turnover rates can disrupt the quality of health services, increase recruitment costs, and hinder continuity of services. This study aims to analyze how the work environment and burnout affect nurse turnover at Husada Hospital, and how work motivation can mediate the relationship. Data were collected through questionnaires filled out by 167 nurses at Husada Hospital, then analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test the relationship between variables. The results showed that the work environment had a significant effect on work motivation, while burnout had a significant negative effect on work motivation. Work motivation was also shown to mediate the influence of the work environment and burnout on nurse turnover. These findings emphasize the importance of improving the quality of the work environment and reducing burnout as an effort to increase nurse work motivation, which can ultimately reduce turnover. This study provides important implications for hospital management in designing policies that support nurse welfare in order to maintain workforce stability.

KEYWORDS: Burnout, Nurses, Turnover, Work Motivation, Work Environment, Husada Hospital

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are a very important asset in a company or organization to achieve success, especially in realizing the company's vision, mission, and goals. The major challenges faced by many organizations include recruiting and retaining quality employees, while many competent workers have not been optimally absorbed in the workforce. A survey by the Central Statistics Agency of Indonesia (BPS, 2024) shows that the unemployment rate, although decreasing, still tends to fluctuate, which is often influenced by economic uncertainty. This uncertainty not only affects the availability of jobs, but also raises concerns among employees seeking career stability, which can increase the desire to change jobs (turnover intention) within the company. Employee turnover in the healthcare industry, especially nurses, is a problem faced by almost all hospitals around the world (Halter et al., 2017). According to Labrague et al. (2020), Nurse turnover not only affects the availability of adequate workers, but also affects the quality of health services provided to patients. Nurse turnover in a hospital can have various impacts, both positive and negative. On the one hand, the turnover of nurses can open up new opportunities for the career development of other nurses, as well as bring in fresh ideas and new approaches that can improve the quality of service.

However, on the other hand, nurse turnover also poses a number of challenges that cannot be ignored. Losing nurses, especially experienced ones, can disrupt continuity of care and reduce the quality of service to patients (Hu et al., 2022). The process of recruiting and training new nurses requires a lot of money and time, while the remaining nurses have to face an increased workload. This can lower team morale and increase the risk of exhaustion and burnout among nurses, which can ultimately affect overall patient safety and satisfaction (Wardhani et al., 2023). The productivity and stability of the business might be disrupted by high turnover, which highlights how crucial good human resource management is. With an annual incidence of around 27.3%, high nurse turnover rates are another issue Indonesia faces (Fitriarsari, 2020). Likewise, this issue is recognized as a complex and multifaceted problem, with factors affecting every sector of healthcare (Labrague et al., 2020). Various factors have been studied and are thought to contribute to high turnover rates. Not all causes of turnover come from internal organizational factors. A study conducted by Cao et al. (2021) in China illustrates that the resilience of each individual can be a supporting factor for turnover. Resilience is defined as a person's ability to respond back from pressure or stressful situations.

Factors that influence it are work environment and physical fatigue. Resilience affects turnover intention indirectly and is significantly related to mediating work environment factors and fatigue. Worrying evidence shows that nurses from the younger generation or Generation Z (1993-1999), tend to be more likely to feel a mismatch between the work environment and their personal

values compared to nurses from older generations such as Generation X (1964-1978) and Generation Y (1979-1992). Generation Z also shows higher signs of burnout and lower levels of commitment to the organization. Work environment and burnout are two major factors that are often associated with nurse turnover. An uncondusive work environment, such as high workload, low social support, and role conflict, can increase stress and burnout levels among nurses (Kohnen et al., 2023). Burnout, characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and decreased personal accomplishment, has been recognized as one of the leading causes of high turnover rates in the nursing profession (Halter et al., 2017). A poor work environment is often the main trigger for turnover. Unsupportive working conditions, such as excessive workload, irregular working hours, and lack of support from management, can decrease job satisfaction and increase the desire to leave the job (Kohnen et al., 2023). Research by Labrague et al. (2020), showed that nurses who work in a less supportive environment are more likely to experience burnout and, ultimately, leave their jobs. Other studies have shown that the work environment is one of the key factors influencing nurse turnover. A conducive work environment, including good relationships between coworkers, supportive management, adequate facilities, and clear policies and procedures, can reduce nurses' desire to leave their jobs. In contrast, an unsupportive work environment, such as high work pressure, interpersonal conflict, and lack of support from management, often triggers nurses to look for work elsewhere (Liu et al., 2023). Burnout or work exhaustion is one of the most discussed issues in the medical world. Burnout experienced by nurses can be caused by excessive work demands, lack of appreciation, and an imbalance between workload and personal capacity. Burnout that is not handled properly will have an impact on nurses' desire to quit their jobs, which then increases the turnover rate. Several studies have shown that burnout is a strong predictor of nurse turnover, especially in those who experience high levels of stress and low social support (Boamah et al., 2022; Cao et al., 2021). At Husada Hospital Jakarta, high levels of burnout among nurses have been identified as one of the main factors driving turnover.

Table 1. Employee Turnover Data 2020-2023

Year	Initial Number of Employees (A)	Employee Entry (B)	Employee Out (C)	Number of Employees End (D)	Turnover Rate	Retention Rate (F)
2020	552	40	56	536	10.29%	89.86%
2021	496	38	36	498	7.24%	92.74%
2022	458	25	49	434	10.99%	89.30%
2023	431	28	51	408	12.16%	88.17%

Source: Data from Husada Hospital Jakarta

At Husada Hospital Jakarta, the nurse turnover rate has shown a fluctuating trend, with the highest peak in 2023, exceeding the threshold considered normal (more than 10%). The main factors influencing turnover include high work pressure, excessive workload, lack of management support, and burnout due to work demands that are not commensurate with the incentives or rewards received. Additionally, the COVID-19 epidemic has significantly affected the turnover rate due to an increase in workload and modifications to organizational dynamics. Work motivation is one of the other elements that can affect how burnout and the work environment affect nurse turnover. Work motivation serves as a mediator that may either amplify or diminish the impact of burnout and the work environment on nurses' decisions to remain or quit their positions, according to Wang et al. (2023). High intrinsic motivation nurses are more resilient to work-related stress and burnout, which reduces their turnover risk.

Work motivation is one of the important factors that can mediate the influence of the work environment and burnout on turnover. Winoto (2019) research where someone with high intrinsic motivation is more resistant to work stress and has a lower level of burnout, so they tend to be more loyal to the organization. In the context of Husada Hospital Jakarta, strengthening nurses' work motivation through career development, training, and recognition can be an effective strategy to reduce turnover. High work motivation can anticipate the negative impact of a poor work environment or burnout on the desire to leave work. Employees who have high work motivation tend to be better able to survive in challenging work situations and are more loyal to the organization. Although the association between work environment, burnout, and turnover among nurses has been the subject of several prior research, very few have examined the function of work motivation as a mediating factor in this relationship. According to these research, nurses' decisions to remain with or quit the company might be significantly impacted by the interplay of work environment

characteristics, burnout, and motivation. However, further research is needed to better understand how work motivation can effectively mediate the relationship in the specific context of hospitals. Husada Hospital is one of the large hospitals in the capital city that faces similar challenges related to nurse turnover. The high rate of nurse turnover in this hospital has triggered the need for more in-depth research to understand the factors that influence nurses' decisions to leave their jobs. This study is considered important because it provides a deeper understanding of how the work environment and burnout affect nurse turnover, as well as how work motivation can act as a mediator in this process. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the development of human resource management strategies at Husada Hospital, as well as in other hospitals facing similar problems.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Turnover intention

Employees who have not yet reached the point of actual relocation are said to have turnover intention, which is the desire or intention to leave one job for another. Turnover refers to the ultimate truth that the business must deal with, which is the amount of workers who depart within a specific time frame. Turnover intention is the degree of employee intention to quit the organization. According to Salvagioni et al. (2017), there are 3 factors that can influence the occurrence of turnover intention, namely; Environmental factors, Individual factors, and Structural factors.

Burn Out

According to Salvagioni et al. (2017), burnout syndrome is a person's reaction to ongoing work stress that progresses over time and may eventually become chronic, resulting in health issues. According to psychological theory, this condition damages people's cognitive, emotional, and attitudinal faculties, which results in unfavorable actions toward users, coworkers, and the profession itself. This is a result of certain aspects of the professional activity rather than personal issues. The World Health Organization claims that burnout is a workplace phenomena rather than a disease. According to Khammissa et al. (2022), it is brought on by unresolved chronic job stress and is defined by feelings of tiredness, a decrease in professional effectiveness, and a growing mental detachment from one's work, negative sentiments, or cynicism connected to one's employment. Burnout was first used in scientific literature by Maslach, who described it as a process of social workers gradually becoming weary, cynical, and less committed. Salvagioni et al. (2017) revised the idea and provided a more exacting and practical definition of burnout as a psychological syndrome marked by depersonalization, emotional exhaustion, and a diminished sense of professional efficacy that can occur years later and following multiple empirical studies.

Work Environment

According to Shin et al. (2023), the work environment in nursing practice is not just a place where nurses carry out their duties, but also has a huge impact on their well-being. A positive and conducive environment can help improve nurses' motivation, job satisfaction, and performance, while a poor environment can have the opposite effect. Some of the main components of the work environment that can affect nurses' well-being at work and affect burnout include workload, social support, recognition and rewards, opportunities for self-development, occupational safety and health, and work-life balance. A work environment that treats employees positively, including in small things such as fair division of labor, involvement of each employee to express opinions and make choices can increase employee loyalty to the work organization. This attachment will foster a sense of belonging to the work environment that supports worker effectiveness and well-being. According to Coco et al. (2023), on the other hand, a bad work environment can also negatively affect nurses' physical and emotional well-being. Long and irregular work hours, together with exposure to physical, chemical, and biological risks, can lead to a number of physical health issues. Therefore, it's critical that healthcare companies focus on and enhance their work environments to make them more supportive of nurses' well-being. Individual nurses will gain from this, and it will also improve the general standard of healthcare services.

Work Motivation

An essential aspect that motivates people to work hard and efficiently is job motivation. Workplace motivation is essential for nurses to deliver high-quality, patient-centered healthcare. According to Tecocalu et al. (2022), motivation stems from a positive mindset that encourages workers to put themselves in circumstances that will help them accomplish company objectives. Nurses' work motivation is influenced by various factors, both from themselves and from the work environment. In terms of internal factors, the needs and values of nurses greatly influence their motivation. Nurses who have needs and values that are in line with nursing goals

tend to be more motivated. Nurses who feel they have adequate skills and knowledge to do their jobs well will be more motivated to work. According to Elnaby et al. (2023), nurses with an internal focus of control are more confident that they have control over their lives and are more motivated to achieve their goals. Nurses who are highly committed to their profession and the organization where they work will be more motivated to work hard. In terms of external factors, good working conditions, such as decent wages, a safe and comfortable working environment, and a reasonable workload, can increase nurses' work motivation.

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual model that illustrates the link between the independent and dependent variables is developed based on the issue definition, study objectives, and theoretical discussion.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Author, 2025

III. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to ascertain how work motivation at Husada Hospital mediates the relationship between burnout and the work environment and nurse turnover. 300 nurses make up the study's population. Random probability sampling was used as the sampling technique in this investigation. A sample collecting method called probability sampling gives every member of the population an equal chance of being chosen as a sample. The number of samples in this study used the Slovin formula with a margin of error of 5%. So that the number of samples needed in the study was around 167 nurses. Primary data in this study were obtained directly from respondents and provided data to data collectors. Data measurement in this study was through distributed questionnaires. A questionnaire is a list or series of questions that are arranged in writing about something related to the research. In addition, there is secondary data from documents, reports, and literature that are relevant to the research topic. The scale used in data measurement is the Likert scale with each measurement answer given a score from a scale of 1 to 5. Data analysis used in this study used Partial Least Square (PLS) which is a component-based or variant Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) equation model. PLS is a powerful analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions (Ghozali, 2018).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Measurement Model Test (Outer Model)

Using SmartPLS 4.0 software, the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach was used to examine the study model. The measuring model illustrates how manifest variables are represented versus latent variables to be measured. Convergent validity is used in the first test, meaning that each construct indicator's loading factor values must be more than 0.7 (confirmatory research) and between 0.6 and 0.7 (exploratory research). The following is a research model design that is analyzed based on the loading factor and indicator values for each variable > 0.7 so that it has met the requirements of convergent validity.

Table 2. Convergent Validity

Variables	Indicator	Loading Factor	Information
Burnout	X1.1	0,760	Valid
	X1.2	0,764	Valid
	X1.3	0,723	Valid
	X1.4	0,736	Valid
	X1.5	0,743	Valid
	X1.6	0,775	Valid
	X1.7	0,804	Valid
Work Environment	X2.1	0,802	Valid
	X2.2	0,802	Valid
	X2.3	0,828	Valid
	X2.4	0.808	Valid
	X2.5	0.783	Valid
	X2.6	0.796	Valid
	X2.7	0.808	Valid
Work Motivation	Z1	0.846	Valid
	Z2	0.824	Valid
	Z3	0,800	Valid
	Z4	0.828	Valid
	Z5	0.805	Valid
	Z6	0.824	Valid
	Turnover Intention	Y1	0.737
Y2		0.733	Valid
Y3		0.765	Valid
Y4		0.733	Valid
Y5		0.742	Valid
Y6		0.717	Valid
Y7		0.737	Valid

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

Based on the table above, all indicators used have a loading factor value > 0.7 so that they can be declared valid. This means that all indicators in the burnout variable, the work environment work, motivation work, and turnover intention have a high correlation and meet the requirements of convergent validity.

Meanwhile, in convergent validity, the AVE value that describes the variance of the manifest variables that can be owned by the latent construct must be greater than 0.5. Based on the table below, all constructs already have a value > 0.5 so that there is no problem of convergent validity in the model being tested.

Table 3. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variables	AVE (Average Variance Extracted)	Validity
Burnout	0.575	Valid
Work environment	0.646	Valid
Work motivation	0.674	Valid
Turnover Intention	0.544	Valid

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

Then the second test is discriminant validity, where there are two approaches used, namely comparing the cross loading value and the Fornell-Larcker criteria (comparing the \sqrt{AVE} of a construct must be greater than the correlation with other constructs).

Table 4. Cross Loadings Factor Values

Item	X1	X2	Z	Y
X1.1	0,760	-0,357	-0,371	0,523
X1.2	0,764	-0,437	-0,468	0,544
X1.3	0,723	-0,351	-0,357	0,458
X1.4	0,736	-0,367	-0,374	0,484
X1.5	0,743	-0,373	-0,395	0,502
X1.6	0,775	-0,456	-0,476	0,494
X1.7	0,804	-0,435	-0,414	0,576
X2.1	-0,334	0,802	0,675	-0,481
X2.2	-0,505	0,802	0,694	-0,620
X2.3	-0,440	0,828	0,691	-0,596
X2.4	-0,456	0,808	0,659	-0,557
X2.5	-0,413	0,783	0,628	-0,521
X2.6	-0,416	0,796	0,664	-0,494
X2.7	-0,379	0,808	0,612	-0,504
Y1	0,508	-0,471	-0,500	0,737
Y2	0,507	-0,455	-0,460	0,733
Y3	0,496	-0,522	-0,578	0,765
Y4	0,487	-0,523	-0,547	0,733
Y5	0,466	-0,539	-0,510	0,742
Y6	0,534	-0,467	-0,432	0,717
Z1	-0,544	0,669	0,846	-0,574
Z2	-0,394	0,672	0,824	-0,494
Z3	-0,368	0,589	0,800	-0,508
Z4	-0,459	0,712	0,828	-0,591
Z5	-0,392	0,725	0,805	-0,570
Z6	-0,490	0,676	0,824	-0,626

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

When compared to other latent variables in the model, the loading value between the indicator and its latent variable is higher. For example, the loading value between X1.1 and X1 is 0.76, which is greater than the loading value between X1.1 and X2 of -0.357; X1.1 and Z of -0.371; X1.1 and Y of 0.523, and so on. Thus, the indicator X1.1 really enters and measures the latent variable of burnout (also applies to variables X2, Z, and Y in the model).

Table 5. Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	Burnout	Work environment	Work motivation	Turnover Intention
Burnout	0.758			
Work Environment	-0.203	0.804		
Work Motivation	-0.209	0.162	0.821	
Turnover Intention	0.377	-0.293	-0.301	0.738

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

The Fornell-Larcker Criterion is satisfied if the diagonal value (square root of AVE) is higher than the value in the corresponding row or column, as shown in the above table. Because every diagonal value in this matrix is higher than the non-diagonal values in the same row and column, discriminant validity is satisfied.

Additionally, dependability assessments were carried out using Assessing the consistency of responses to the questionnaire's statement questions across time is the goal. Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha values serve as the foundation for reliability choices. If the Composite Reliability value is greater than 0.7 and the Cronbach's Alpha value for all variables is greater than 0.6, even if it approaches 1, then the construct is deemed trustworthy.

Table 6. Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha Values

Variables	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
Burnout	0.879	0.877	reliable
Work Environment	0.910	0.909	reliable
Work Motivation	0.905	0.903	reliable
Turnover Intention	0.833	0.833	reliable

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

It can be inferred that the independent factors, namely Burnout and Work Environment, the mediating variable Work Motivation, and the dependent variable are all greater than 0.7 based on the Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha values. The questionnaire for Turnover Intention has trustworthy statement items that can yield consistent responses over time.

Structural Model Test (Inner Model)

The structural model is used to test the relationship or relationship between exogenous and endogenous latent variables that have been hypothesized previously. The structural model test is carried out by looking at the value of the coefficient of determination and the relevance of the prediction. A good coefficient of determination value is when it approaches 1, because it means that the independent variable provides almost all the information needed to predict the variation of the dependent variable.

Table 7. Results of the Determination Coefficient Test

Matrix	R-square value	Information
Burnout & Work Environment → Work Motivation	0.693	Moderate
Burnout, Work Environment, & Work Motivation → Turnover Intention	0.620	Moderate

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

R² value of 0.693 indicates that the magnitude of the variation in the work motivation variable (Z) that can be explained by the variation in the independent variables burnout (X1) and work environment (X2) is 69.3%. This value is more than > 0.50, so it is included in the moderate category. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.620 for the influence of organizational culture, work environment, and work motivation together on turnover intention indicates that the variation in the turnover intention variable (Y) that can be explained by burnout (X1), work environment (X2), and work motivation (Z) is 62.0%. This value is in the range of 0.33-0.67, so it is included in the moderate category.

In addition to using R-Square, model evaluation can be seen from the Q-Square predictive relevance value with the criteria that if Q² > 0, then it has more accurate predictive relevance. Here is the calculation of the Q-Square value using the formula:

Table 8. Q Square Test

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Work Motivation (Z)	1002,000	541,643	0.459
Nurse Turnover (Y)	1002,000	675,711	0.326

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

It can be observed that the Q^2 value ranges from $0 < Q^2$. Since the variables of work motivation and nurse turnover have $Q^2 > 0$, it can be concluded that the model has predictive relevance.

Hypothesis testing based on t-statistics and probability (p-value) can be seen from the following bootstrapping results.

Table 9. Direct Influence Value

Variables	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Std Deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics	P-Values
Burnout → Work Motivation	-0.149	-0.150	0.048	3,077	0.002
Burnout → Turnover Intention	0.405	0.408	0.060	6,775	0,000
Work Environment → Work Motivation	0.745	0.745	0.048	15,366	0,000
Work Environment → Turnover Intention	-0.236	-0.230	0.111	2,122	0.034
Work Motivation → Turnover Intention	-0.272	-0.278	0.117	2,331	0.020

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

It is known that the direct effect of burnout on turnover ($X1 - Y$) has a t-statistic value of $6.775 > 1.96$ and a p-value of $0.00 < 0.05$, with a coefficient value of 0.405, so it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted, burnout has the potential to significantly increase turnover intentions among nurses at Husada Hospital.

Then the work environment on turnover ($X2 - Y$) has a t-statistic value of $2.112 > 1.96$ and a p-value of $0.034 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted, with a coefficient of -0.236, then a bad work environment can significantly increase turnover intentions among nurses at Husada Hospital.

The direct effect of burnout on work motivation has a t-statistic value of $3.077 > 1.96$ and a p-value of $0.002 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted, with a coefficient of -0.149, which means that an increase in the level of burnout is negatively related to the work motivation of nurses at Husada Hospital significantly.

Furthermore, the direct influence of the work environment on work motivation has a t-statistic value of $15.366 > 1.96$, p-value $0.000 < 0.05$, and a coefficient of 0.745, so it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted. The influence of a good work environment can increase the work motivation of Husada Hospital nurses very significantly.

Finally, a t-statistic value of $2.331 > 1.96$, a p-value of $0.020 < 0.05$, and a coefficient of -0.272 indicate that work motivation has a negative relationship with nurse turnover, with high work motivation lowering the intention of Husada Hospital nurses to change jobs. Based on these findings, the hypothesis is accepted.

The indirect effect of the following bootstrapping findings can be used to estimate the size of the mediation role for the intervening variable:

Table 10. Indirect Influence Value

Variables	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Std Deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics	P-Values
Burnout → Work Motivation → Turnover Intention	0.041	0.039	0.017	2,325	0.020
Work Environment → Work Motivation → Turnover Intention	-0.203	-0.209	0.092	2,194	0.028

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

It is known that the indirect effect of burnout on turnover intention through work motivation has a p-value of $0.020 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is a mediating role of work motivation in influencing burnout on turnover intention of nurses at Husada Hospital, Jakarta. Additionally, the p-value for the indirect relationship between the work environment and nurses' intention to leave their jobs through work motivation is $0.028 < 0.05$, indicating that the hypothesis is accepted and that work motivation plays a mediating role in the relationship between the work environment and nurses' intention to leave their jobs at Husada Hospital in Jakarta.

Discussion

The results of the first hypothesis test showed that burnout had a significant effect on increasing turnover intention, supporting previous studies (Kurniawaty, 2019; Rahmawati, 2023; Irmadela et al. 2023). This means that the higher the level of burnout, the more likely the nurse is to intend to leave their job. Most nurses in the analyzed population had moderate to low levels of burnout, with low turnover intention. This reflects the effectiveness of resource management and management in the healthcare industry, which contributes to nurses' loyalty to their jobs. However, there are still nurses with high levels of burnout and turnover intention, so hospital management needs to identify the causes of burnout and implement strategic steps to prevent it.

Furthermore, the work environment has a significant effect on nurses' turnover intention at Husada Hospital. Good work environment conditions, such as harmonious relationships between nurses, positive relationships with leaders, support from coworkers and superiors, adequate facilities, and appreciation for contributions, play an important role in increasing nurses' comfort and loyalty. Conversely, a less supportive work environment can increase the intention to leave the job. This finding is consistent with previous studies Purwati & Maricy (2021), Sazili (2022), and Kurniawaty (2019), which stated that a positive work environment reduces turnover intention. Psychological factors, such as good relationships between employees, are prominent aspects in supporting job satisfaction at Husada Hospital, thus maintaining workforce stability.

A significant relationship was also found between burnout and work motivation. Burnout, which is caused by chronic stress due to excessive workload and lack of support, has a negative impact on employee work motivation. Decreased motivation is seen in the indicator of low drive to complete work according to target, which reflects reduced commitment to work and the organization. This condition can reduce productivity and quality of performance, and has the potential to increase employee turnover. In line with the findings of Talahatu (2018) and Salvagioni (2017). Burnout, which is caused by chronic stress due to excessive workload and lack of support, has a negative impact on employee work motivation. Decreased motivation is seen in the indicator of low drive to complete work according to target, which reflects reduced commitment to work and the organization.

The results of the subsequent hypothesis testing showed a significant influence between the work environment and work motivation, supporting previous studies by Marzuqi (2021) and Rahim et al. (2017). A conducive work environment has been shown to increase work motivation, while a less supportive environment can decrease it. Based on the questionnaire analysis, the work environment had the highest average score, indicating that the majority of employees rated it as good. At Husada Hospital, the work environment significantly affects nurses' work motivation, which directly affects work enthusiasm and indirectly shapes their perceptions of work goals and career sustainability.

Work motivation has a considerable impact and is inversely correlated with turnover intention, according to the findings of testing the fifth hypothesis. These findings corroborate earlier research by Winoto (2019) and Ambarsari et al. (2019), which found that employees are less likely to want to quit a firm when they are more motivated to do their jobs. There are two ways to look at the connection between job motivation and the intention to leave. If work motivation is not supported by opportunities to develop or achieve career goals, high motivation can trigger turnover intention. However, if work motivation is supported by factors that create satisfaction and recognition in work, work motivation can actually reduce the intention to resign.

The sixth hypothesis was then tested, and the results showed that work motivation played a substantial role in mitigating the impact of organizational culture on turnover intention. Accordingly, work motivation may operate as a mediator between employee desire to quit and burnout. Reduced burnout will boost motivation at work, which will lower a company's intention to fire employees. These findings corroborate other studies by Ike et al. (2019), Ambarsari (2019), and Winoto (2019) that found a mediation link between turnover intention and motivation and work satisfaction. When work motivation increases again, employees will feel more connected to their work and stronger to survive even though they experience stress or burnout. This can strengthen employee mentality in facing challenges and commitment to their work. It is important for organizations to pay attention to employee welfare and provide the necessary support so that work motivation is maintained and turnover intention can be minimized.

According to the seventh hypothesis, there is a considerable impact of work motivation in moderating the impact of the work environment on turnover intention. This indicates that the link between the work environment and the desire to leave is significantly mediated by job motivation. Employee motivation can rise in a favorable work environment, which lowers the likelihood of turnover. These findings corroborate earlier research by Ike et al. (2019), Ambarsari (2019), and Winoto (2019) that found a mediation link between turnover intention and motivation and work satisfaction. The link between the work environment and the intention to leave is mediated in part by job motivation. When the work environment is good and supportive, employees who feel motivated are more likely to stay with the company and continue to work with enthusiasm. Highly motivated employees feel that their work is meaningful, and they are better able to overcome existing challenges.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between burnout, work environment, work motivation, and turnover intention in nurses at Husada Hospital, Jakarta. Work motivation has been shown to have an important mediating role in the relationship between burnout and turnover intention, as well as between work environment and turnover intention. Burnout has a significant effect on increasing turnover intention, where the higher the level of burnout, the more likely nurses are to leave their jobs. A conducive work environment has been shown to increase work motivation and reduce turnover intention. Low work motivation, as a result of burnout, reduces employee motivation to complete work according to target, thereby increasing turnover intention. Conversely, high work motivation, supported by a positive work environment and appreciation for employee contributions, can reduce the intention to leave work. Overall, these findings indicate the importance of efforts to manage burnout, create a supportive work environment, and strengthen work motivation in order to maintain employee loyalty, increase productivity, and minimize turnover intention.

It is recommended that companies improve open communication to support innovation by providing a platform for employees to convey new ideas. Management also needs to provide an understanding of innovation risk management, as well as provide awards, training, and comparative study programs to support employee self-development in terms of career, knowledge, and experience. In addition, companies can implement periodic Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess employee performance more comprehensively, so that evaluation and improvement steps can be carried out more quickly and effectively. To overcome burnout, mindfulness and resilience training programs, such as meditation, breathing techniques, and the use of mindfulness applications, can be implemented. Companies can also create facilities such as Wellness Lounges with various relaxation features to help nurses manage stress. Finally, an evaluation of work facilities, especially related to air comfort in the workspace, needs to be carried out by considering the addition of ventilation or humidifiers to create a healthier and more comfortable work environment.

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